

LEGAL LIABILITY FOR VIOLATION OF RIGHTS IN THE FIELD OF COPYRIGHT

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Abstract

Language teaching and learning programs provide students the opportunity to discover how languages are learned and how they may be most-effectively taught. These programs allow students to consider questions including the subsequent: What theoretical troubles underline the teaching and studying of language?

Key words: language, learning, teaching, second language, communication, speech,

Abstract: Today, attention to intellectual property objects is increasing against the background of the general increase in interest in cultural objects observed in the world.

The legislative consolidation and protection of the rights of authors and other copyright holders to intellectual property objects is a prerequisite for the development of the industry worldwide.

Keywords intellectual property, copyright, protection, liability (civil, administrative, criminal).

The author or other copyright holder of property rights to works of fine art has the exclusive right to the lawful use of this intellectual property object at his discretion, in any form and by any available means.

In addition to property rights, the authors of works of fine art have personal non-property rights. The person who violated these rights is brought to legislative responsibility.

Copyright infringement refers to the use of works of science, literature and art without the appropriate permission of the authors or copyright holders, as well as violation of the terms of the contract, if the latter is present. In this case, legal liability is inevitable.

In this paragraph, we will analyze the types of legal liability, as well as article by article consider the sanctions provided for violation of the rights of authors. But before proceeding to the analysis, we need to know the answers to such questions as: how long are the rights of authors protected? Who are they guarded by? What methods of copyright protection exist?

So, the allocation of authors' rights into two different groups, we assume, is also due to different terms of protection of these rights.

According to the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, copyright is valid throughout the life of the author and 70 years after his death¹, while the calculation of the seventy-year period begins on January 1, following the year in which the legal fact of the death of the author or other copyright holder took place². Let's take an example. In April 2021, the honored sculptor, Honored Artist of Uzbekistan Yakov Shapiro³ passed away, the works of fine art created by him, the exclusive rights to which he retained, will be protected for 70 years. At the same time, the calculation of the term begins on January 1, 2022, and will continue to be protected until December 31, 2092. After that, the sculptures created by him will go into the public domain. And the right to the name of the author, the right of authorship and the right to protect the reputation of the author will be protected indefinitely.

This copyright term is not a universal term for the protection of the exclusive rights of the author or copyright holder. Other options for calculating the term are as follows⁴:

- For works legitimately published under a pseudonym or anonymously – 50 years after its publication (if the identity of the author is revealed during this time, then the usual term of protection will apply to this work);
- For works created in collaboration – the whole life of the authors, and 70 years after the death of the last of the authors;
- For works first published after the death of the author – 70 years after its release.

The state acts as the guarantor of the protection of property and personal non-property rights in our country⁵.

Regarding the ways of protecting rights, civil legislation establishes general measures (Article 11 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan). In addition to them, Article 1040, it is possible to protect the exclusive rights to intellectual property objects by removing the material objects with which the exclusive rights are violated; at the same time, necessarily publishing

¹ The Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (part two) of 29.08.1996 – [Electronic resource]. – Access mode: <https://lex.uz/docs/180550>

² The Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (part two) of 29.08.1996 – [Electronic resource]. – Access mode: <https://lex.uz/docs/180550>

³ <https://www.gazeta.uz/ru/2021/04/04/shapiro/>

⁴ The Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (part two) of 29.08.1996 – [Electronic resource]. – Access mode: <https://lex.uz/docs/180550>

⁵ Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan

information about the violation, mentioning the subject whose rights are violated⁶.

Let's move on to the consideration of legal liability.

In the legal literature, there is a classification of types of legal liability based on various criteria. One of the most common criteria is an industry attribute. The classification of liability by branches of law is determined by the peculiarities of regulation in each of the branches, as well as the nature of offenses and legal consequences for the violator⁷.

There are several types of liability for copyright infringement on works of fine art:

Civil liability is a liability to the copyright holder that arises in the event of a violation of property rights to a work. The copyright holder has the right to claim compensation for damage caused by the violation of his rights.

Administrative liability - copyright infringement may lead to the imposition of an administrative fine or other administrative measures by government agencies.

Criminal liability - infringement of copyright on a work may be recognized as a criminal offense and entail criminal punishment.

Bringing to legal responsibility for violation of the intellectual rights of the author is aimed at restoring the violated law and order. In this regard, the most frequently applied measure is to bring to civil liability. In accordance with article 1070 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a party that has not fulfilled or fulfilled the terms of the copyright agreement improperly is obliged to compensate for losses caused to the other party, including lost profits⁸. In such cases, the existence of a contract is the basis for the application of legal measures. Moreover, in case of violation of personal non-property rights, it is possible to claim compensation for moral damage.

In case of violation of the exclusive right to certain types of results of intellectual activity, the rightholder has the right to receive compensation for violation of this right, which he can claim instead of damages. By its nature, compensation is a special civil sanction for non-contractual harm⁹.

⁶ The Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (part two) of 29.08.1996 – [Electronic resource]. – Access mode: <https://lex.uz/docs/180550>

⁷ Bazylev B.T. Legal responsibility. Krasnoyarsk, 1985.pp. 31-47; Dukhno N.A., Ivakin V.I. The concept and types of legal liability // State and law. 2000. No. 6. pp. 12-13; Lipinsky D.A. About the system of law and types of legal responsibility // Jurisprudence. 2003.

⁸ The Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (part two) of 29.08.1996 – [Electronic resource]. – Access mode: <https://lex.uz/docs/180550>

⁹ Intellectual Property law. Vol. 1. General provisions: Textbook / Under the general editorship of D.yu.n., prof. L.A. Novoselova. – M.: Statute, 2017.

Further, having considered the Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Administrative Responsibility, we found that with respect to copyrights, an administrative offense is recognized as: illegal use of works, as well as reproduction, distribution, bringing to the public counterfeit copies of works or objects of related rights or the indication of false information on copies of works or objects of related rights about their manufacturers, places their production, as well as about the copyright holders. We will not dwell on the mentioned ways of using the work, as we revealed them in the first chapter of the work.

Sanctions measures are of greater interest. Thus, violation of copyright and related rights entails the imposition of a fine on citizens from 1 to 5 basic calculated values, and on officials – from 5 to 10 BRV, while counterfeit copies of works are confiscated. Slightly stricter penalties are provided for offenses committed repeatedly within a year after the application of administrative responsibility, which is from 5 to 10 and from 10 to 20 for citizens and officials, respectively.

The last type of legal liability for intellectual property infringement is criminal liability.

Criminal liability is established for such actions as attribution of authorship, coercion to co-authorship of intellectual property objects, as well as disclosure of information about these objects without the author's consent before their official registration or publication¹⁰, It is given in the disposition of article 149 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Attribution of authorship in the legal literature is understood as plagiarism. Attribution of authorship (plagiarism) can manifest itself in various forms, including declaring oneself the author of someone else's work, releasing a fully or partially copied work under one's own name, publishing a work created in collaboration with other people, without mentioning their names.

Summarizing the above, it can be concluded that the institution of legal responsibility for copyright infringement on works of fine art exists on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, but its functioning can be considered as insufficiently effective, since the number of offenses and crimes in the field of copyright is growing every day. We note that such an increase is associated with relatively weak sanctions measures. For example, in case of an administrative offense, a fine of 1 to 5 BV is imposed on a citizen, which today amounts to 330.000 - 990.000 soums. Given the possible profit from the illegal use of works, it can be argued that the amount of the fine is insignificant.

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